

Method for solving the Algebraic Equations of Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: This paper presents a method to solve the algebraic equations taken away from two distinct combinatorics geometric series. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to compute the multiple summations of a geometric series [1-13], a new idea stimulated his mind to create a new type of geometric series. As a result, a combinatorial geometric series [11-20] was developed with new idea of binomial coefficients.

2. System of Binomial Coefficients

The combinatorial geometric series is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial geometric series [17-32] refers to the binomial coefficient [29-42].

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i,$$

$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ denotes the combinatorial geometric series and V_n^r the binomial coefficient.

$N = \{V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_4^1, \dots\}$ is a set of natural numbers or system of binomial coefficients.

Let us show that V_n^r belongs to the set of natural numbers, *i. e.* $V_n^r \in N$,

where, $V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!}$ and integers $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$.

$V_0^1 = 1; V_1^1 = 2; V_2^1 = 3; V_3^1 = 4; V_4^1 = 5; V_5^1 = 6; \dots$

Let $V_n^r = V_{Q-1}^1$, where $Q = V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!}$.

$$V_{Q-1}^1 = \frac{(Q-1+1)}{1!} = Q \quad (OR) \quad V_{V_n^r-1}^1 = \frac{(V_n^r-1+1)}{1!} = V_n^r.$$

$\therefore V_n^r$ belongs to the set of natural numbers, *i. e.* $V_n^r \in N$.

3. Algebraic Equations

Let us take away two algebraic equations from two different combinatorial geometric series as follows:

$$V_k^r x^k + V_{k+1}^r x^{k+1} = c_1 \text{ taken away from } \sum_{i=0}^p V_i^r x^i \text{ and}$$

$$V_k^n x^k + V_{k+1}^n x^{k+1} = c_2 \text{ from } \sum_{i=0}^q V_i^r x^i, \text{ where } c_1 \text{ and } c_2 \text{ are numerical constants.}$$

By solving the algebraic equations in the usual way, we get the following solution for x^{k+1} :

$$x^{k+1} = \frac{V_k^n c_1 - V_k^r c_2}{V_k^n V_{k+1}^r - V_k^r V_{k+1}^n}.$$

By substituting the value of x^{k+1} in one of the above algebraic equations, we can find the solution for x^k .

4. Conclusion

In this article, a method was introduced for solving the algebraic equations taken away two distinct combinatorial geometric series. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real world problems.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2022) Application of Factorial and Binomial identities in Information, Cybersecurity and Machine Learning. *International Journal of Advanced Networking and Applications*, 14(1), 5258-5260. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-pnx53-v21>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2022) Algorithmic Approach for Computation of Binomial Expansions. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4260689>.
- [3] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation and Calculus for Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Identities and Expansions. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(7), 14648–01i. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss7pp14648-01i>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2022) Construction of Novel Binomial Expansion. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4269024>.
- [5] Annamalai, C. (2022) Novel Multinomial Expansion and Theorem. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4275263>.
- [6] Annamalai, C. (2022) A Theorem on Binomial Series. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4275263>.
- [7] Annamalai, C. (2022) Factorials, Integers and Mathematical and Binomial Techniques for Machine Learning and Cybersecurity. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4174357>.

- [8] Annamalai, C. (2022) Combinatorial and Multinomial Coefficients and its Computing Techniques for Machine Learning and Cybersecurity. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(8), 14713–01i. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss8pp14713-01i>.
- [9] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation and Analysis of Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Series. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4253238>.
- [10] Annamalai, C. (2022) Two Different and Equal Coefficients of Combinatorial Geometric Series. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4250564>.
- [11] Annamalai, C. (2022) Lemma on the Binomial Coefficients of Combinatorial Geometric Series. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(9), 14760-01i. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss9pp14760-01i>.
- [12] Annamalai, C. (2022) A Theorem on Successive Partitions of Binomial Coefficient. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4228510>.
- [13] Annamalai, C. (2022) Sum of Successive Partitions of Binomial Coefficient. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4226966>.
- [14] Annamalai, C. (2022) Skew Field on the Binomial Coefficients in Combinatorial Geometric Series. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(11), 14859-01i. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss11pp14859-01i>.
- [15] Annamalai, C. (2022) Scalar and Vector Space of Combinatorial Geometric Series. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4225265>.
- [16] Annamalai, C. (2022) Construction and Analysis of Binomial Coefficients. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4223597>.
- [17] Annamalai, C. (2022) Series and Summations on Binomial Coefficients of Optimized Combination. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(3), 14123-01e. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss3pp14123-01e>.
- [18] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computing Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Expansion. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4168016>.
- [19] Annamalai, C. (2022) Ascending and Descending Orders of Annamalai's Binomial Coefficient. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4109710>.
- [20] Annamalai, C. (2022) A Binomial Expansion Equal to Multiple of 2 with Non-Negative Exponents, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4116671>.
- [21] Annamalai, C. (2022) Alternative to the Binomial Series or Binomial Theorem, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4228921>.

- [22] Annamalai, C. (2022) Real and Complex Numbers of Binomial Coefficients in Combinatorial Geometric Series. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4222236>.
- [23] Annamalai, C. (2022) Annamalai's Binomial Expansion, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4262282>.
- [24] Annamalai, C. (2017) Analysis and Modelling of Annamalai Computing Geometric Series and Summability. *Mathematical Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences*, 6(1), 11-15. <https://doi.org/10.15415/mjjs.2017.61002>.
- [25] Annamalai, C. (2017) Annamalai Computing Method for Formation of Geometric Series using in Science and Technology. *International Journal for Science and Advance Research In Technology*, 3(8), 187-289. <http://ijsart.com/Home/IssueDetail/17257>.
- [26] Annamalai, C. (2017) Computational modelling for the formation of geometric series using Annamalai computing method. *Jñānābha*, 47(2), 327-330. <https://zbmath.org/?q=an%3A1391.65005>.
- [27] Annamalai, C. (2018) Novel Computation of Algorithmic Geometric Series and Summability. *Journal of Algorithms and Computation*, 50(1), 151-153. <https://www.doi.org/10.22059/JAC.2018.68866>.
- [28] Annamalai, C. (2018) Computing for Development of A New Summability on Multiple Geometric Series. *International Journal of Mathematics, Game Theory and Algebra*, 27(4), 511-513.
- [29] Annamalai, C. (2020) Combinatorial Technique for Optimizing the Combination. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 6(2), 0189-0192. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl6iss2pp0189-0192>.
- [30] Annamalai, C. (2018) Annamalai's Computing Model for Algorithmic Geometric Series and Its Mathematical Structures. *Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 3(1),1-6 <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.mcs.20180301.11>.
- [31] Annamalai, C. (2022) Partition of Multinomial Coefficient, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4213629>.
- [32] Annamalai, C. (2022) My New Idea for Optimized Combinatorial Techniques, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4131592>.
- [33] Annamalai, C. (2022) System of Novel Binomial Coefficients and Series, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4320197>.
- [34] Annamalai, C. (2022) Extension of Binomial Series with Optimized Binomial Coefficient, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4129875>.

- [35] Annamalai, C. (2019) Recursive Computations and Differential and Integral Equations for Summability of Binomial Coefficients with Combinatorial Expressions. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Mechanical and Materials Engineering*, 4(1), 6-10. <https://ijsrmme.com/IJSRMME19362>.
- [36] Annamalai, C. (2018) Algorithmic Computation of Annamalai's Geometric Series and Summability. *Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 3(5),100-101. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.mcs.20180305.11>.
- [37] Annamalai, C. (2022) Summation of Series of Binomial Coefficients, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4215918>.
- [38] Annamalai, C. (2022) Multinomial-based Factorial Theorem on the Binomial Coefficients for Combinatorial Geometric Series, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4203744>.
- [39] Annamalai, C. (2022) Differentiation and Integration of Annamalai's Binomial Expansion, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4110255>.
- [40] Annamalai, C. (2022) A Generalized Method for Proving the Theorem derived from the Binomial Coefficients in Combinatorial Geometric Series, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4209479>.
- [41] Annamalai, C. (2020) Abelian Group on the Binomial Coefficients in Combinatorial Geometric Series. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(10), 14799–01i. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss10pp14799-01i>.
- [42] Annamalai, C. (2022) Analysis of Combinatorial Binomial Coefficients and Series, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4324303>.